

English Instructions Electronic Bookin Improving English Young Learner Teacher’s Skill in Indonesia

Euis Yanah Mulyanah, Ishak

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 03, 2021

Accepted:
December 06, 2021

Keywords :

English instructions,
English young learners,
Teacher’s skill

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5762385

Abstract

Based on the results of previous research, conducted by Mulyanah & Ishak 2020 from University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang-Indonesia, from the observation, there has been a phenomenon in the field that there are still English teachers who are not linear with their fields of expertise, especially in remote areas in the Tangerang region. In addition, teachers are also not motivated to increase their potential as young learner English teachers. This certainly has an impact on the score student learning outcomes that have been the standards of the government. The purpose of this research is to provide young learner English teachers facilities in order to develop their potential through electronic book media for teacher interesting learning process, motivates and can improve their English skills. The sample taken was 40 from English Elementary School teachers located in Tangerang District-Indonesia. The results showed that English instructions electronic book can improve motivation and English skills, especially for English teacher for young learners because English instructions electronic book one of media to make easy and motivated for the young English teachers in the learning process in improving their English skill.

Introduction

The research is an advanced study of previous research that is still related to improving English skills for teachers at the Elementary School Level located in the Tangerang Regency. Based on the results of research conducted by Mulyanah from the University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang with the results of research including: In 2018, research focused on student learning outcomes through the TPR method in English learning process and the conclusion, that students' abilities improved with these methods, but there is a problem that arises, namely the lack of human resources in English teachers' skill (Mulyanah & Ishak, 2018). In 2019, the research was re-developed by focusing on improving teacher competence in English mastery, which then resulted in the conclusion of improving the competence of English mastery in teachers in Tangerang both in the city and in Tangerang regency, but raised new problems, namely the lack of media such as adequate books as teacher companion books in teaching English (Ishak & Mulyanah, 2019). The year 2020, focuses on research from the use of teacher companion printed books to facilitate in teaching English with the conclusions of the book is very effective for teachers in teaching English (Mulyanah & Ishak, 2020). On the basis of the background of the researchers above, the basic research is carried out where this research is a development of the results of PDP research in the last three years. (1) How to improve the English language skills of elementary teachers in Tangerang? (2) how to apply electronic book media in improving teachers' English language skills in Tangerang? and (3) its effective use of e-book English instructions in improving the ability of elementary teachers in Tangerang? Special purpose, the creation of ISBN electronic books that can help teachers in 4 improve the sustainability of The English language and facilitate in providing instructions in English to students properly and correctly. The aims of this research is to increase human resources, especially for young learners' English teacher in Tangerang-Indonesia with training and mentoring those results in an increase in teacher competence.

Research problem

Based on the results of previous research in the PDP scheme in 2020 found that 80% of teachers are still reluctant to use English in teaching learning process, this is due to two factors including: 1) The teachers lack English vocabulary, 2) The teachers feel insecure, 3) The teachers are embarrassed and afraid of English mispronunciation in the learning process of teaching in the classroom. And 4) The lack of available media such as a book guidance for teacher learning process is easy to practice in everyday teaching, resulting in an influence on the results of students' declining English use. However, there is no further research on English Instructions e-books that can be accessed by teachers, through this ranking can facilitate teachers in accessing electronic books both offline and online (Mulyanah, 2018).

Research Hypothesis

There has been a very significant increase in improving the ability to discuss English teachers through English instructions as an electronic book medium for English teachers for young learners in Tangerang-Indonesia.

Theoretical Foundation

In this research is the development of printed books used by teachers into an electronic book so that it facilitates in its use so that it is necessary to review the library as one of the applications of the use of e-book English instructions for young learner's English teachers, where in it there is an explanation of how to provide instructions properly and correctly through English instructions and the use of electronic books. Some of the theories and literature reviews are as follows:

Vocabulary

Vocabulary is one of the aspects of language that supports when people learn about language (Ortalisje&Metboky, 2020). Not only does one need to know the meaning of a particular word, but all aspects of a word must also be understood. So, the language skills that must be possessed by teachers is the ability to give commands or instructions in English (Rostini, Mugara, Nafiqoh (2020).Because in this case language learning cannot be separated from one's ability to learn vocabulary as the key to one's success in communicating (Mega, 2018). Vocabulary is a word and a word is a small life of human life. According to Nation, vocabulary is the link of language activity (Ishak & Mulyanah, 2019).According to Richard in Thornbury's book, vocabulary is a core component of language skills and is the basis for students to speak, hear, read and write. From the three theories it can be concluded that, vocabulary is one aspect that must be learned by humans in learning language in other words that vocabulary is the most important part to facilitate communication (Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019).Mastery of vocabulary will be successful if learned using interesting techniques, fluent pronunciation and very high confidence. But found in the field when teachers master enough vocabulary, teachers are usually reluctant to use it in everyday learning in the classroom, it is because teachers are not confident and afraid of making mistakes in saying it.In addition, the teacher does not yet know how to teach English vocabulary using interesting techniques (Mulyanah & Ishak, 2020). From some of the opinions above, it can be concluded that when we know a lot of vocabulary it will make it easier for us to communicate. Knowledge of vocabulary can be achieved when there is interaction with the interlocutor through instructions using English.

English Instructions

English instructions are based on observations of the way babies get their native language, which generally takes place in the form of conversations in which children give a physical response to the instructions of parents or others around them. For example, when a father says: "Look at dad" or "Give me the ball" the child will do it (Madisa&Suariah, 2019).Through the above explanation, English instructions are language teaching techniques designed to enable students to acquire new expressions, especially verbs and other accompanying words, through listening and performing these words and can also be applied with individual learning style (Rissanes, *at all*, 2019). In learning, students don't have to talk. Their main task is to carry out the commands spoken by the teacher (acting as parents) repeatedly until smoothly (Sulfemi & Kamalia, 2020). This means that in the level of practice, the teacher begins learning by saying a command in the form of a word (such as: "Jump!" or Read!") or a phrase (such as: 'look at the board') and perform actions in accordance with the command. After that, the teacher returned to say the order and all the students did it. After repeating the same activity several times, the teacher can assign students to say the command and at the same time perform it. Once each student feels confident in his or her mastery of the word or phrase, the teacher can assign students to change roles to give and perform the instructions (Syafrijal & Haerudin, 2021) (Hasibuan, 2020).

To teach English vocabulary using English instructions, teachers can follow various procedures that have been prepared by experts that can be obtained in bookstores that provide lesson materials for school purposes. In addition, teachers can also arrange their own teaching procedures that are tailored to the needs of their students.What must be remembered is that the words to be taught must be able to be performed so that their meanings can be understood by students (Solihat& Riansi, 2018) (Uzer, 2019).

Method

The research methods used are as follows: Stage 1, researchers use a quantitative descriptive approach with quasi experimental designs because it performs a way to compare groups. The type of quasi experimental designs selected is nonequivalent control group design by including pretest and posttest in the experimental and control classes in determining the ratio of ability level scores before and after treatment.Stage 2, researchers drafted in preparation for the creation of customized electronic books using the Book Creator app. After the

draft is completed, researchers made a manual for the use of electronic books and then the application of the e-book to 40 young learners' English teachers as a sample.

Test

Table 1. Results of Pretest and Posttest Score of the Control Group

Control	Min	Max	Average	Std.Dev
Pretest	29	87	70.20	19
Posttest	39	98	86.20	13
<i>Gain</i>	10	11	16.00	
Percentage	26%	11%	19%	

Table 2. Results of Pretest and Posttest Score of the Control Group

Group	POSTTEST			
	Min	Max	Average	Std.Dev
Experiments	30	95	78.70	18
Control	30	89	77.50	16
<i>Gain</i>	0	6	1.20	
Presentation	0%	7%	2%	

Table 3. Results of Pretest and Posttest Grades of the Experiment Group

Experiment	Min	Max	Average	Std.Dev
Pretest	39	98	86.20	13.06
Posttest	30	89	77.50	16
<i>Gain</i>	9	9	8.7	
Percentage	30%	10.11%	11.23%	

Results and Discussion

Observation

Based on the results of observations on the ground, there are several problems, but what must be quickly overcome is the unavailability of learning media in the form of electronic books for teachers that can improve the motivation and English language skills of young learner English teachers in Tangerang regency.

Figure 1. Diagram of Posttest Score Differences between Experiment and Control Groups

Based on Table 3 above, it shows an increase in the number of scores in the final test of the experiment group when compared to the control group. The experiment group achieved an average score of 86.20 while the control group achieved an average score of 77.50. So, the increase in the score in the form of percentage obtained from the experiment group was 11.23% after the experiment group received treatment. Furthermore, according to Figure 1 (bar diagram), the highest score of the final test was found in the experiment group that reached 98, it can also be seen that there is also an increase so that the treatment has been successful in improving motivation and English language skills through English instructions electronic book at young learner English teachers in Tangerang-Indonesia.

Conclusion

This research was conducted on the basis of improving the English language skills of teachers found in Tangerang Regency, especially for young learner English teachers. The Researcher use a quantitative descriptive approach using quasi experiment design (Nonequivalent Control Group Design). Pretest and posttest were given to the experiment and control group, thus finding the comparative score

between before and after the two groups received treatment using the Means of English Instruction Electronic Book. Sampling from teachers found in Tangerang regency as many as 40 people. The results of this study were seen in the average score on the final test which reached 86.20 in the experiment group, while for the final test score obtained in the control group was 77.50 which eventually there was an increase in percentage of 11,237%. Hypothesis in this study shows H_0 rejected and H_a accepted can be stated based on the above statement that the improvement of English skills teachers has been successful by using English instructions electronic book in learning. The novelty of this research is that printed books become more innovative electronic books in terms of shape and appearance, making it easier for teachers to learn them wherever and whenever they want them.

Recommendations

This research can be recommended as a strategy to teach teachers in improving the skills of English that is interesting and interactive in the learning process in class because this electronic book can help teachers to learn wherever and whenever teachers can improve their English language skills by using their smartphones.

Acknowledgements

The researcher is very grateful to Majelis Pendidikan Tinggi, Penelitian dan Pengembangan, Pimpinan Pusat Muhammadiyah, who had funded the implementation of this research at the Muhammadiyah Batch V Research Grant in 2021. Number of contract: 0842.400/PD/L.3/C/2021. Thank you also to LPPM Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang who has supported the implementation of this research.

References

- Hasibuan, S. W. 2020. Studi Kegagalan Intruksi Kelas di Kursus Bahasa Inggris essential Medan. *Jurnal PAI Makrifat*. 4 (1): 52-63
- Ishak & Mulyanah, E. Y. 2019. Laporan Akhir Penelitian PDP MENRISTEKDIKTI 2019: Implementasi Metode Total Physical Respons (TPR) dalam Meningkatkan Kemampuan Bahasa Inggris

- Guru SD di Tangerang.
- Ishak & Mulyanah. E.Y. 2019. *English Instructions for Primary School Teacher*. Tangerang: CV. Sagara Mukti.
- Madisa, &Suariah. 2019. The Influence of the Principal’s Leadership on Teacher Teaching Performance in Improving the Quality of Graduates. *JPSD*, 5 (2), 159–165.
- Mega, I. R. 2018. The Relationship Between Students’ English Interest and Vocabulary Mastery Toward Writing Ability. *Scientia*. 3 (2): 121-141
- Mulyanah E.Y., Ishak, Firdaus. M. I. 2018. Laporan Akhir Penelitian PDP MENRISTEKDIKTI 2018: Metode Total Physical response (TPR) dalamPenguasaanKosa Kata Bahasa InggrisSekolah Dasar (SD).
- Mulyanah, E. Y. & Ishak. 2020. Laporan Akhir Penelitian PDP RISTEKBRIN 2020: Implementasi English Instructions Book Sebagai Media PembelajarandalamMeningkatkan Bahasa Inggris Guru SD di Tangerang
- Mulyanah. E.Y. 2018. Using PowerPoint Program in Improving Students’ Vocabulary Mastery. *Globish (An English-Indonesian journal for English, Education and Culture) Journal*. 6 (1): 25-31
- Mulyanah, E,Y&Ishak. 2020. English Instructions Media Book in Improving English of Elementary School Teachers in Tangerang. *JPSD*.6 (2):174-184
- Ortalisje, D. E. &Metboki Y. 2020. PembelajaranKosakata Bahasa Inggris pada Mahasiswa Program Studi Bahasa Inggris. *JurnalLingko: JurnalKebahasaan dan Kesastraan*. 2 (1): 21-36
- Puspitarini, Y. D., & Hanif, M. 2019. Using Learning Media to Increase Learning Motivation in Elementary School. *Anatolian Journal of Education*, 4(2), 53–60.
- Rissanen, I., Kuusisto, E., Tuominen, M., &Tirri, K. 2019. In search of a growth mindset pedagogy: A case study of one teacher’s classroom practices in a Finnish elementary school. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 77, 204–213.
- Rostini, S., Mugara, R. &Nafiqoh, H. 2020. MeningkatkanKosa kata Bahasa InggrisMelaluiPermainanPesanBerantaiDengan Media Gambar Pada kelompok B di Ra Al-Islamiyah. *Jurnal Ceria (CerdasEnergikResponsifInovativeAdaptif)*. 3 (4): 282-289
- Solihat, I. &Riansi, E. S. 2018. LiterasiCerita Anak DalamKeluargaBerperanSebagaiPembelajaranPembentukanKarakter Anak Sekolah Dasar. *JPSD*. 4 (2) 258-271
- Sulfemi, W. B., &Kamalia, Y. 2020. Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Model using Audiovisual Media to Improve Learning Outcomes. *JPSD*, 6(1), 30–42.
- Syafrizal, S., &Haerudin, H. 2018. the Implementation of Vocabulary Building Strategy in Teaching English Vocabulary to Young Learners. *Jo-ELT (Journal of English Language Teaching)*, 5(1), 40–48
- Uzer. Y. 2019. ImplementasiPembelajaran Bahasa Inggris Anak MelaluiMetodeGerak dan LaguUntuk Anak Paud. *PERNIK Jurnal PAUD*. 2 (1): 145-155

Author Information

Euis Yanah Mulyanah

University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang
 Jl. PerintisKemerdekaan 1/33 Cikokol, Tangerang-
 Indonesia

Ishak

University of Muhammadiyah Tangerang
 Jl. PerintisKemerdekaan 1/33 Cikokol, Tangerang-
 Indonesia
